
A Brief Conceptual Comparative Analysis of ASP Reasoners and Multi-Agent Reasoners for Predictive Maintenance and Failure Prediction in Battery Systems

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1 Introduction

Accurate prediction of battery failure is crucial for ensuring reliability, safety, and longevity in energy storage systems across diverse applications, from electric vehicles to renewable energy grids. Effective battery management relies on analyzing multivariate time-series data to capture the dynamic and evolving characteristics of battery degradation Lipu et al. (2022). Traditional predictive maintenance methods, including reactive (run-to-failure) and scheduled (time-based) approaches, often entail high costs, significant risks, and either premature or delayed maintenance interventions, Fioravanti et al. (2020). Consequently, there is a critical need for more sophisticated methods that can deliver early failure detection and accurate degradation forecasting, thus enhancing operational safety, system reliability, and significantly reducing maintenance costs and downtime.

2 Method and Experiments

Recent advancements in predictive maintenance have introduced a range of methodologies, such as in Chen (2020); Cavus et al. (2025) from a rule-based threshold checks to complex data-driven models. In this work, we propose a brief conceptual comparative analysis of two symbolic AI reasoning approaches: Answer Set Programming (ASP) as in Lifschitz (2019) and Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) as in Šarunas Raudys and Zliobaite (2006); Salvador Palau et al. (2019), utilizing the NASA Prognostics Batteries dataset introduced by Saha and Goebel (2007). This dataset comprises comprehensive cycle-by-cycle measurements, including voltage, current, temperature, capacity, and impedance, from Li-ion batteries subjected to varied operational profiles (charge, discharge, and impedance)

In the ASP-based framework as illustrated in Figure 1a, raw battery cycle data is initially subjected to preprocessing and feature extraction. A sliding window method is applied to the processed time-series data to mitigate the effects of transient anomalies and measurement errors. Subsequently, the data within each sliding window is converted into a structured set of logical facts suitable for reasoning in ASP. Expert domain knowledge is then encoded into declarative rules, defining specific conditions for battery failure. For example, a rule may state that if the measured capacity during a discharge cycle falls below 1.4 Ahr (a 30% fade from the rated capacity of 2 Ahr), then the battery is considered to have reached its end-of-life. ASP solvers then compute answer sets that explicitly reveal the battery's state by enforcing these constraints. This method offers high transparency and a clear traceability of the decision-making process, which is especially valuable for diagnosing specific degradation events

In the proposed MAS framework shown in Figure 1b, we aim to deploy multiple specialized agents, each monitoring a specific aspect of battery data such as capacity, impedance, voltage,

and temperature. Each agent processes incoming real-time data streams, assesses them against predefined thresholds, and communicates potential anomalies through established message-passing protocols. For instance, a dedicated 'Capacity Agent' identifies and flags cycles where the battery capacity falls below critical thresholds, while an 'Impedance Agent' monitors abnormal impedance trends. A central coordinator, the 'Diagnosis Agent,' aggregates alerts from these diverse agents, synthesizes the findings, and generates dynamic, real-time predictive maintenance decisions. This decentralized structure ensures adaptability and real-time responsiveness, essential for promptly adjusting assessments as new data becomes available.

Figure 1: Conceptual workflows of two symbolic AI approaches for predictive battery maintenance. (a) ASP-based framework using rule-based reasoning for generating maintenance alerts. (b) MAS-based framework with distributed agents collaborating for predictive maintenance decisions.

3 Discussion and Outlook

At this stage, we anticipate distinct strengths and limitations from each method. We expect that ASP would excel in transparency and explainability because it explicitly uses human-readable logical rules to interpret battery states. However, we also foresee potential limitations regarding computational complexity and scalability, particularly for large datasets or real-time scenarios, due to the resource-intensive nature of grounding and rule-solving processes. Conversely, we anticipate that MAS would demonstrate advantages in real-time responsiveness, adaptability, and scalability because of its distributed and modular architecture. However, MAS may offer only moderate transparency due to the complexity arising from multiple interacting agents. This conceptual analysis provides an initial framework to guide future practical evaluations and helps in identifying which criteria will be crucial for eventual benchmarking.

In summary, a conceptual framework comparing two symbolic AI reasoning methods: ASP and MAS for predictive battery maintenance has been presented. In future research practical validation and quantitative comparison will be provided. We aim to implement and experimentally validate both approaches, assessing key performance metrics including accuracy, computational efficiency, transparency, scalability, and real-time responsiveness. Additionally, we plan comprehensive benchmarking against established predictive methods such as classical machine learning and deep learning to confirm their practical applicability.

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